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ARCHITECTURE IN ISTANBUL DURING THE REPUBLICAN PERIOD

Abstract. Istanbul, one of Turkiye's 81 provinces, the largest city of geographical, historical and socio-cultural importance, ranks first in Europe in terms of population, 21st in the world after Lagos, Nigeria, and 34th in the world in terms of economic size.

Istanbul, which developed as an imperial capital for hundreds of years and transformed with new spaces by experiencing the modern urbanization process during the 19th century, entered the 20th century as an important world city and an imperial capital. After the first decade of the new century, the period that led to the destruction of the empire through wars and defeat in World War I, became a troubled period for the capital Istanbul, both politically, economically and culturally. At the end of this process, in which change in the urban space can occur to a limited extent, Istanbul, which lost its identity as the imperial capital, After the declaration of the Republic and the election of Ankara as the capital, Significant changes have also occurred in its physical structure [1].

Key words: Republic, Istanbul, Taksim, Beyoglu, Bosphorus Bridge.

Introduction. The city had already lost its population in the wars that determined the period leading to the end of the empire; After the bureaucracy members left Istanbul due to Ankara becoming the capital, the population of Istanbul, which was over 1,000,000 in the early 1920s, was halved at the end of the decade [2].

The Republican administration, which prioritized the construction of the capital Ankara and Anatolian cities, did not invest much in Istanbul in its first years. It is observed that foreign capital, which was effective in the modernization of the city during the late Ottoman period, also withdrew from the city within the framework of the nationalization policy of the Republic. Therefore, no significant spatial change was observed in Istanbul in the 1920s, when the new administration experienced difficulties both politically and economically. Nevertheless, in the Early Republic period, the urban space in Istanbul, as throughout the country, was shaped by state initiatives rather than private enterprises [1].

Fig. 1. Beyazıt Square

Fig. 2. Taksim Square. İstanbul

The interpretation of the main material

1. Boulevards, squares and parks. In the first years of the republic, it is noticeable that new squares were built, which played a significant role in the modernization of the city. Beyazıt Square (Fig.1), located in the center of the historical peninsula, was shaped as a public open space in 1923–1924, according to the design of Asım Kömürcüoğlu, with a pool with a fountain in the middle. This practice is followed by the arrangement of Taksim Square (Fig.2), which defines the point extending from the historical peninsula to the new residential areas of the city [3].

With the shaping of the pedestal and environmental layout according to the design of Giulio Mongeri and the installation of the Republic Monument designed by Pietro Canonica, the most important element of the square, in 1928, Taksim Square (Fig. 2) was defined as the representative place of the Republic administration in the city and the center of national ceremonies.

When it is remembered that in the last century of the Ottoman Empire, the center of Istanbul transcended the historical peninsula and led to new developments, especially in the Galata-Pera regions, it would not be surprising to see that this bi-focused spatial development even after the Republic [3]. The Unkapanı (Atatürk) Bridge, which developed as another important center of 20th century Istanbul and connected the Historical peninsula to Beyoğlu, the fact that its construction started in 1927, in the first years of the Republic, is an example of the restructuring of the city with a holistic approach (Fig.3).

Following the competition organized under the name of planning the capital Ankara with the slogan of “modernization” of the cities of the Republic, a master plan preparation competition was announced in Istanbul, as in many cities, in 1933 [4].

Fig. 3. Unkapanı bridge built over the Golden Horn

Fig. 4. Atatürk Boulevard view from Aksaray

Perhaps the most important of these new axes is the Atatürk Boulevard, which was opened in 1941 to connect the Golden Horn (Haliç) to Yenikapı by ensuring the continuation of the Atatürk Bridge, which connects Beyoğlu to the historical peninsula, on the peninsula (Fig.4). Similarly, during this period, while the Eminönü-Unkapanı line was opened on the historical peninsula, Galata-Tophane and Taksim-Tepbası were opened and developed on the Beyoğlu side, and Bagdat Street was opened and developed on the Kadıkoy side. In this process, along with the reshaping of Sultanahmet, the most important square of the historical peninsula, Sirkeci Square in front of the train station was also completed and put into use.

The most important initiatives carried out in this region are the demolition

Fig. 5. Eminonu New Mosque square

Fig. 6. Dolmabahce square

of many buildings deemed “worthless” in Eminönü Square in front of the Yeni Cami (New Mosque), and the demolition of some old buildings in Beyazıt Square to create a large open public space [4].

In this process, efforts to preserve large-scale structures simultaneously increased, for example, along with the demolition of the small buildings around them, the New Mosque (Yeni Cami) (Fig. 5), and Spice Bazaar (Mısır Çarşısı) in Eminönü Square, and the Beyazıt Mosque in Beyazıt Square were repaired, it is seen that they were unearthed as monumental structures that define and “beautify” the squares.

The Karakoy Square, which was formed as a counterpart to Eminonu Square on the Beyoglu side, was formed in the same way, by tearing down pre-existing structures. On the European side, the Kabatas, Dolmabahce (Fig. 6) and Barbaros (Beşiktaş) squares, and on the Anatolian side the Uskudar and Kadikoy squares were formed in a similar way, completing the piers. Following the example of urbanization that was implemented by Haussman in the 19th century, this practical implementation of modernization not only created squares and boulevards that were intended to establish the “new” city feel, but the old structures were sacrificed. Important buildings from the older structure were identified as “eternal” and their protection was brought to the fore.

The design made by Henri Prost, who was invited to Istanbul in 1936 and worked in this field until 1951, with the aim of creating a “beautiful city”, included not only the squares he called “free areas”, but also open spaces consisting of walking parks and paths, and viewing terraces [5].

In the 1930s and 1940s, many green areas in Istanbul such as Abbasaga, Aksaray, Anadoluhisari, Ayasofya (Hagia Sophia), Bakirkoy, Heybeliada, Tarabya, Visnezade, Yenikoy, Yesilkoy, Yogurtcu parks were opened to the public. In addition to these small-scale parks, the most important one, both with its large scale and its impact on the formation of Istanbul’s urban and public identity, is the area defined as “Park No. 2” in the Prost plan.

In the 19th century, with the destruction of the auxiliary buildings to Taksim Artillery (Topcu) Barracks, which were constructed during the era of Sultan Abdülmecid, was demolished in the early 1940s, Taksim Square was widened and landscaped; after this, with the destruction of the barracks structure itself, a terrace and park was formed to the north of the square.

This park, known as Taksim Gezi, or in Commemoration of the president of the era, İnönü Gezi, joins the Taksim Garden in the north, which was opened in 1868 as one of the first public park arrangements of the Ottoman Empire; from here it is connected to “Park No.2” [5].

With the shaping of Taksim Square as a public open space and the construction of Park No. 2, which the Prost plan defines as the largest green area of the city, located in the north and east of the square, the region has become, It has developed as a city center since the 1930s. Forming Istanbul’s largest designed open public space, this area plays a huge role in planning the “beautification” of the city and the “modernization” of urban life.

Fig. 7. Ataturk Cultural Center. Taksim

Fig. 8. Open Air Theater (Harbiye Cemil Topuzlu)

2. Entertainment, Culture and Education.

When the interventions made in Taksim Square and its surroundings in the 1940s are considered together with Park No.2, it can be seen that a design that restructured the city center as a public space was realized and the region turned into a “cultural valley”. In addition to the creation of a public green area called “Taksim Gezisi” in the part of Park No.2 facing Taksim Square, in one corner of Gezi, Taksim Casino, designed by Ruknettin Guney, was built in 1938, and on the side of Park No.2 opening to the sea, Taşlık Kahvesi (Taslik Coffee), designed by Sedad Hakkı Eldem, was built in 1948 [5].

In the area where buildings were demolished to the east of Taksim Square, the construction of the Opera House started in the mid-1940s, based on the projects of Ruknettin Guney and Feridun Kip, but was completed in the 1960s as the Ataturk Cultural Center (Fig. 7), in accordance with the project of Hayati Tabanlıoğlu, and also, it increased its role in the cultural life of the region and the city with the Open Air Theater (Fig.8), (Harbiye Cemil Topuzlu), designed by Nihad Yucel and Nahid Uysal in 1946–1947, located on the natural slope of the park.

In the same period, in the area of the park extending to Dolmabahçe, which was obtained as a result of the demolition of the palace stables, in 1947, the stadium designed by Paolo Vietti-Violi, Sinasi Sahingiray and Fazıl Aysu, and named after

the then President “İnönü”, was built (Fig. 9).

On the northern border of the park, the Sports and Exhibition Palace (Fig. 10) named after Governor Lutfi Kirdar, who carried out the improvement initiatives of the time, was designed and built by the same architects in 1949. In 1945, the Istanbul Radio House, located in the northwest of the park area, was built with the projects of Dogan Erginbas, Ismail Utkular and Omer Gunay. Thus, starting from Taksim Square, which took on a ceremonial character with the Republic, this area grew with public open spaces and buildings, and since the 1940s, it has become a recreation center with the most important sports, entertainment and cultural activities in Istanbul.

People’s Houses (Community Centers) were added to the new entertainment and cultural centers established around Taksim Square and Taksim Gezi Park and in Park No 2 in the 1930s and 1940s. Although most of these institutions were housed in historical buildings, among the seventeen community centers opened in Istanbul by the 1950s, there were also new buildings, such as the Kadıkoy People’s House designed by Ruknettin Guney, which won a competition in 1939. Ruknettin Guney worked in Istanbul Municipality, during the period of Lutfu Kirdar – between 1938–1951 – when the public places of the city center were designed and made important, he worked as a regional manager in the last stage of the administration and as the author of the architectural works of many buildings in the city center, he is an architect who made pioneering contributions to modern Istanbul.

Fig. 9. İnönü stadium

Fig. 10. Sports and Exhibition Palace)

Among the buildings he implemented during his tenure in the municipality: Taksim Municipal Casino, Tennis Fencing and Mountaineering Club, which he developed together with Fazıl Aysu, and Florya Municipal Casino [5].

Educational buildings take an active part in the urban space; However, since these institutions generally carried out their functions in historical buildings, they did not have a very important role in new architectural construction. Istanbul University, which started to use the Ministry of War building and took a key position in Beyazıt Square, in the center of the historical peninsula, The Academy of Fine Arts, located in Çifte Saraylar on the Bosphorus, Istanbul Technical University, which is located in the Taşkılla building near Taksim, or Yıldız Technical University, which uses some of the Yıldız Palace buildings, as seen in the examples, higher education institutions of the period generally adopted and used historical buildings from the Ottoman period, and there was no need to build new buildings for these institutions for a while.

Although many primary and secondary education buildings used converted historical buildings, there were also newly built educational buildings, as seen in the example of Fındıklı Primary School, which was completed in 1932–1934 with the design of the French architect Georges Debés.

While new school buildings were designed in a modernist, simple language according to the architectural approach of the period in the 1930s, designs with historical references were seen in the 1940s.

The additional building, built for the Faculty of Science – Literature of Istanbul University in 1943 with the design of Sedat Hakkı Eldem and Emin Onat, is one of the most important examples of the period style defined as “second national” (Fig. 11).

On the other hand, despite the strong central character of Beyoğlu and Taksim regions, modern life is not limited to the city center. Located on the periphery of the city, of which The Florya Marine Mansion, designed by Seyfi Arkan for President Atatürk in the mid-1930s, is an important example; The residences in Yesilköy, Kadıköy and the islands, as well as summer resorts for entertainment and relaxation such as beaches, pools and clubs, spread the new lifestyle from the center of Istanbul to the surrounding districts [6].

Near Sultanahmet Square, one of the most central places of the historical peninsula, where the administration has been located since the Ottoman period.

It can be said that there was no other administrative structure that stood out in the definition of urban space until the Palace of Justice (Fig. 12), which was built in 1948 with the design of Sedat Hakkı Eldem and Emin Onat.

Fig. 11. Faculty of Science – Literature of Istanbul University

Fig. 12. Sultanahmet courthouse building

3. Urban Interventions.

With the addition of the practice of filling sea shores in the 1960s and 1970s, coastal roads were opened on both sides of the Bosphorus; The Levent-Buyukdere-Maslak line, which accelerated the northward movement of the European side, was developed and Bagdat Street, which accelerates the urban development of Kadıkoy by forming the main axis of the Anatolian side, was expanded.

One of the most decisive applications for Istanbul in this period is the Bosphorus (Atatürk) Bridge, where the project of connecting the two sides of the Bosphorus, which has been dreamed of since the IX century, was realized in 1973. The structural design of the suspension bridge, whose piers are located on the shores of Ortakoy on the European side and Beylerbeyi on the Anatolian side, was carried out by Freeman Fox & Partners Company. The steel ropes carrying the bridge, which is 1,560 m long, 33.40 m wide and 64 m high, are supported by 165 m high towers forming the piers on both sides (Fig.13).

Fig. 13. Bosphorus (Ataturk) Bridge

Conclusion. Although criticism due to its possible urban and environmental impacts during the construction process created great controversy, The Bosphorus Bridge, completed in the 50th year of the Republic, was followed by the Fatih Sultan Mehmet Bridge, which was built in the northern part of the Bosphorus in the second half of the 1980s; and in 2016, the third bridge named after Yavuz Sultan Selim, which defines the city's outer line close to the Black Sea, was put into service.

Today, Istanbul, which is growing day by day with modern business centers, residences, luxury sites, shopping malls, industrial, commercial and public buildings, has a special place in world architecture as one of the selected cities of the 21st century.

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CUMHURİYYƏT DÖVRÜNDƏ İSTANBUL MEMARLIĞI

Türkiyənin 81 vilayətindən biri, coğrafi, tarixi və sosial-mədəni əhəmiyyətli ən böyük şəhəri olan İstanbul, əhalisinə görə Avropada birinci, dünyada isə Nigeriyanın Laqos şəhərindən sonra 21-ci, iqtisadi böyüklüyünə görə dünyada 34-cü sırada yer alır.

Yüz illər boyu inkişaf edərək XIX əsrdə şəhərsalma baxımından müasir urbanizasiya prosesi yaşayan, XX əsrə mühüm dünya şəhəri və imperiya paytaxtı kimi daxil olan İstanbul üçün baş verən müharibələr, eləcə də I Dünya Müharibəsindən sonrakı illər siyasi, iqtisadi, mədəni cəhətdən

çətin bir dövrə çevrildi. Cümhuriyyətin elan edilməsi və Ankaranın paytaxt seçilməsindən sonra imperiya paytaxtı kimliyini itirmiş və milli dövlətə keçid dövründə İstanbulun fiziki və multikultural strukturunda homogenləşməyə doğru bir çox dəyişiklik baş verdi.

Açar sözlər: Cümhuriyyət, İstanbul, Taksim, Bəyoğlu, Boğaziçi körpü.

Сеvindж Тангудур (Азербайджан)

АРХИТЕКТУРА СТАМБУЛА РЕСПУБЛИКАНСКОГО ПЕРИОДА

Стамбул, одна из 81 провинций Турции, крупнейший город как географического, исторического и социально-культурного значения, по численности населения занимает первое место в Европе, 21-е место в мире после Лагоса (Нигерия), и 34-е место в мире по развитию экономики.

Войны, как и годы после Первой мировой войны, стали политически, экономически и культурно сложным периодом для Стамбула, который развивался на протяжении сотен лет и переживал современный процесс урбанизации в XIX веке с точки зрения городского планирования и вступивший в XX век как важный мировой город и имперская столица. После провозглашения республики и избрания Анкары столицей в физической и мультикультурной структуре Стамбула произошло множество изменений, который утратил свою идентичность имперской столицы и превратился в национальное государство.

Ключевые слова: Республика, Стамбул, Таксим, Бейоглу, Босфорский мост.